

FEASIBILITY STUDY ON A LARGE CHOPPER DISC FOR A TOF SPECTROMETER

V. Antonelli^{1*}, W. Lohstroh², H. Baier¹

¹ Institute of Lightweight Structures, Department of Aerospace Engineering, Faculty of Mechanical Engineering, Technische Universität München, Munich, Germany,

² Forschungs Neutronenquelle Heinz-Maier-Leibnitz (FRM II), Technische Universität München, Munich, Germany

* Corresponding author (antonelli@lb.mw.tum.de)

Keywords: *Neutron Spectroscopy, Chopper Disc, Design Optimisation, Feasibility Study, CFRP*

1 Introduction

The European Spallation Neutron Source (ESS [1]) is a multi-disciplinary research centre that will be built in Lund, Sweden. This new generation long pulse source spallation source will have a high flux and a unique time structure. With the first neutron expected in 2019, the instrumentation suite is currently under development. Since the ESS will be a pulsed neutron source, almost all instruments will rely on the time-of-flight technique, i.e. the neutron energy will be determined by its time-of-flight. For this purpose a multitude of different chopper devices are needed for instance for beam shaping, monochromatizing or to avoid overlap between subsequent pulses. They all have different requirements concerning diameter and rotational speed.

At the ESS, it is expected that the guides needed to transport neutrons from the source to the respective instrument will have sizes up to $0.4 \times 0.4 \text{ m}^2$ which therefore require large chopper devices with very large apertures.

The present paper describes the results of a preliminary parameter study on large disc diameters.

2 Background

An example for a time-of-flight spectrometer is shown in Fig. [1] which depicts the layout of the cold neutron spectrometer TOFTOF located at the Forschungsneutronenquelle Heinz Maier-Leibnitz (FRM 2) in Munich. It allows the investigation of a great variety of topics, e.g. diffusive processes in liquids and melts, high-frequency acoustic

propagation, optical vibrational modes, magnetic excitations and tunnelling spectroscopy. TOFTOF utilizes a cascade of choppers to produce a pulsed monochromatic beam which then impinges on the sample. The disc rotation speed (up to 22 000 rpm) mainly defines the length of the pulse that hits the sample. From the time-of-flight from sample to detector, the neutron energy after the scattering is determined.

Figure 1 Schematic plan of the time of flight spectrometer TOF-TOF at FRM II [2]

2.1 Chopper Disc

A chopper disc is a circular disc with a central circular cutout, through which the rotating axel is fixed. On the outer part of the disc one or more apertures, or “windows”, are present through which the neutrons are passing. The outer area of the disc is coated with a neutron absorbing material, typically ^{10}B . The opening time to the disc is therefore determined by the time the window opens the

neutron guide, hence from the angle of the aperture and the rotation speed.

Usually, the first chopper pulses the neutron beam. A second chopper just in front of the sample selects neutrons within a narrow range of speeds. Additional choppers remove “contaminant” wavelengths and reduce the pulse frequency at the sample position.

Counter-rotating chopper pairs (located closely together) with a certain speed behave like single choppers with twice that speed.

Figure 2 Example of CFRP chopper discs [4].

Current state-of-the-art chopper discs have a maximal operating speed of 20,000 rpm and an outer diameter of 0.7 m maximum (independently of the number of apertures and their dimension). The discs rotate in a housing where vacuum is applied.

The weight of the disk is also an important parameter as this determines the power of the engine needed to rotate the disc. This makes the disc weight an important design parameter

A parameter that is becoming more important is the first global eigenfrequency of the disk. When the first eigenfrequency is lower than the operational speed, the disk needs more time during the acceleration up to the operational speed and during slowing down. In particular, when a sudden stop is needed due to some system failure, it is better to have a stiff disc that is able to stop quickly

compared to a lighter, less stable disc. In practice, a trade-off is often needed to find the optimal compromise between low weight and high stiffness

2.2 Manufacturing

The first chopper discs were originally made of metal alloys, due to the isotropic material properties that relax the criticality of the design restrictions, especially around the cutouts. The price of the raw material and easiness of production are the key reasons to stick for so long to this manufacturing process.

In the last decades, higher rotational speed were required as well as larger diameters, and fibre composites are preferred, due to their high specific strength.

For chopper production, carbon fibre pre-preg is used, hardened in an autoclave between two steel moulds to obtain the best performances in terms of fibre volume content and outer shape.

The boron coating is co-cured during this process. Trimming of the disc and fabrication of the features such as windows and the balancing holes is done by milling.

3 Parameter Study

The advantage of a completely new research centre is the freedom of design of each instrument. However, it is foreseeable that ESS will have a number of instruments located at long distances from the source of neutron production. Advanced neutron guide systems to transport the neutrons to the instruments require rather large dimensions up to 0.4x0.4m² and hence also the diameter of the chopper discs will increase. The objective is to design chopper discs able to use the complete neutron beam.

The purpose of the present work is, therefore, to have an estimation of the maximum speed achievable by a chopper disk of one-meter diameter with two large symmetrical apertures. The outcome should provide the physicists with the necessary information to be able to design the most performing instrument.

The parameters that have been varied are the following:

- 3 window angles 30°, 40°, 50°
- 3 window depth 20, 30, 40 cm

The internal diameter of the disc, necessary to accommodate the interface between the disc and the axle is set to 50 mm, while the external diameter is 1 m. All combinations of geometry are shown in Figure 3.

In order to reduce computational time, the symmetry of the disk has been considered and only one quarter of the disk has been modelled. Appropriate symmetric boundary conditions are applied at the two edges of the model.

Figure 3 Geometry of the different discs.

In the case of the discs with windows of 40 cm depth, it is already visible from Figure 3 that the producibility of such a disc is hardly feasible. The reason is that there is a too small amount of material between the edge of the window and the central hole of the disc. This, beside the low expected ultimate speed. Will make it very difficult to design a connection between the axle and the disc. The analysis was carried out mainly for comparison purposes.

In a later phase, a larger diameter, for the same slot dimensions, could be considered.

As the disks are relatively thin, the eigenfrequency of each disk is calculated for each configuration as reference. The eigenfrequency, compared to the

calculated ultimate speed, can always be increased with an increase in weight, which has to be taken into account when the preliminary design of the instrument is carried out.

4 Design optimisation

An optimisation of the thickness distribution is carried out based on a linear static analysis. The disk is divided in concentric rings, as shown in Figure 4, each of them having a thickness equal to a multiple of a “basis thickness” made of 8 layers of prepreg in quasi-isotropic layup: (0/45/90/-45)s.

Figure 4 Example of the definition of the different regions for the assignment of the material properties.

The regions are defined in view of manufacturing considerations and the functional requirements of the disc.

The disk is in fact manufactured superimposing circular pre-preg layers with different diameters on the two mould halves in order to obtain the desired cross-section. The thickness increases from the larger diameter to the inner.

The regions numbered 8 to 16, have to fulfil a structural requirement. The area around the cut-outs, in fact, will present high stress concentration. A change in thickness in these most loaded areas, therefore, will cause an increase of interlaminar shear stresses as well, which consequently, with a change of thickness and therefore stiffness, will

increase the chance of delaminations. This is mostly valid for the region 8, which is regarded as the most critical area. In the case of region 16, a larger area of constant thickness is considered to allow for an easy fixation of the interface between axle and disc.

In the final design, a third wider area of constant thickness has to be created in order to manufacture the holes needed to balance the disk (as also shown in Figure 2). As the balancing holes are small, it is assumed that an area with constant thickness in a not highly loaded area can be easily defined in a later stage and does not influence the parameter analysis.

Given the material characteristics of the pre-preg used (see Table 1 for material properties), the basic thickness step, allowing for a quasi-isotropic symmetric laminate, is 1.3 mm.

E ₁ [MPa]	E ₂ [MPa]	ν ₁₂	G ₁₂ [MPa]	G ₁₃ [MPa]	G ₂₃ [MPa]	thickness [mm]
149,100	6500	0.3	3000	3000	2400	0.1625

Table 1 Material properties of M30SC.

The optimisation aims at finding the maximum speed for a disc with a maximum weight of 10 kg. The output gives the optimal thickness distribution in a 10 kg weight disk at a certain speed.

An inertial load (rotational speed) is applied to the model.

5 Results

All disk were optimised with respect of maximal ultimate speed with a limit for the maximum weight set to 10 kg.

	30°	40°	50°
20 mm	330 Hz	310 Hz	300 Hz
30 mm	270 Hz	270 Hz	260 Hz
40 mm	190 Hz	220 Hz *	220 Hz **

Table 2 Maximal speed of the optimised discs. The weight of each disc is about 10 kg except for * 8 kg and ** 7.5 kg.

In almost all optimisations, the maximal ultimate speed was reached for a weight of 10 km, only the

disks with the deepest slots the ultimate speed was reached at lower weight level but he ultimate speed being much lower than in the case of smaller slots.

An example of the optimised thickness distribution is shown in Figure 5 were the disc with the smallest slot is taken as a feasible solution.

Figure 5 Thickness distribution in the case of slots of 20 mm depth and 30° angle.

The thickness increases slowly up to the edge of the slot where a considerable reinforcement is needed. After that, the thickness increases quite regularly up to the central hole.

Figure 6 principal strains distribution in the case of slots of 20 mm depth and 30° angle.

Figure 6 shows the maximal principal strains the disk. The maximum peak in strain is due to stress concentration around the two cut-outs, as expected. In the other areas, the strains are well below the ultimate value.

The first global eigenfrequency is calculated for the optimised disc design. In Figure 7

Figure 7 First eigenfrequency (197 Hz) in the case of slots of 20 mm depth and 30° angle.

In a detail design stage, the thickness changes will be smoothed and the final design verified, including details, such as the interface between disc and axle and its connection to the disc.

Figure 8 Thickness distribution in the case of slots of 40 mm depth and 50° angle.

Different is the case of the largest and deepest slots, as shown in Figure 8 for a 40 mm deep slot and 50° angle.

There is, in fact, not enough space to hold the disk, therefore the disk thickness around the central hole needs to be very high, compared to the rest of the disc, to achieve enough stiffness. Due to this reason, it is also not possible to increase the mass of the disk over a certain limit due to the difference in stiffness around the hole and around the slot's edge, which gives high stress concentrations.

If such a large slot is preferred, and the envisioned ultimate speed is acceptable, it is advisable to increase the diameter of the disc as the limit weight is not reached.

In Figure 9 the ultimate speed, expressed in rpm, versus the slot depth is plotted for the three different slot angles.

Figure 9 Ultimate speed of the optimised disks.

The figure shows an almost linear behaviour with results within the same range for equal slot depth. The depth of the window is therefore influencing in a greater extent the maximum speed of the disc.

The eigenfrequency of all the discs is well below the ultimate speed. This might be acceptable for some applications, but certainly not for all. The main problem of having eigenfrequencies that are lower than the operational speed is that during both acceleration and deceleration the disc will pass through its eigenfrequency. When the disc is accelerating or decelerating during operation this is

not a problem, as this mean that both operations will be carried out in a controlled way. In case of an abrupt stop, though, it might cause problems. This could be a problem in case of a failure of the system.

If the value of the eigenfrequency is not acceptable; it can be increased by increasing the overall weight of the disc. This does not greatly influence the performances of the disc in terms of ultimate speed, but it does to the overall system needed to speed the disc up to the operational speed.

Figure 10 Calculated eigenfrequency of the optimised disks.

6 Discussion

It has been shown that for a weight of 10 kg, ultimate speeds up to 20,000 rpm can be reached. Considering a safety factor on the speed of 10 %, a feasible operational speed could be around 18,000 rpm in the case of slots of 20 mm.

Figure 11 Difference between a square slot and a triangular one.

Remaining questions are the shape of the slots and the possibility to even lighter discs.

The slots can be, in fact, cut as rectangular as shown in the analysis carried out so far, or as a triangular disc section, as shown in Figure 2. The difference in overall dimension between the two slot designs for the same disc is shown in Figure 11.

In order to verify the influence of the slot's shape and the maximum weight limit, two further analyses were carried out.

6.1 Lightweight disc

In the case of a lightweight disc, a limit weight of 6 kg has been set during the optimisation procedure. The ultimate speed in this case is 290 Hz, 12% less than the original design. The major difference lies in the first natural eigenfrequency, which is less than half of the original design, as shown in Table 3.

	standard	light	difference
Weight [kg]	10	5.8	42.00%
Ultimate speed [rpm]	19800	17400	12.12%
1st eigenfrequency [Hz]	197	97	50.76%

Table 3 Difference between the standard and the lightweight design.

6.2 Slot shape

The ultimate speed for a 10 kg disc with a triangular slot is 15,600 rpm, which is in the same order of magnitude of the square one, as shown in Table 4.

	square	triangular	difference
Weight [kg]	10	10	-
Ultimate speed [rpm]	15600	15000	3.85%
1st eigenfrequency [Hz]	135	167	-23.70%

Table 4 Difference between the square and the triangular slot design.

Though being larger, the square shape has the advantage of having the upper edge of the slot further away from the centre of the disc, which balances the larger dimensions of the disc.

The different thickness distribution, as shown in Figure 12, influences positively the first eigenvalue, which is higher than the square slot design, but still well below the ultimate speed of the disc, as summarised in Table 4.

Figure 12 Thickness distribution for a triangular slot.

7 Conclusions

The results of the feasibility study show that it is possible to design discs with an ultimate speed varying from 200 Hz up to 330 Hz depending mostly on the depth of the slot.

The stresses are overall quite high; a lower speed is therefore preferred.

The optimisations did not take into account the producibility of the disks as this was not the purpose of this parameter study. In some cases, in fact, the thickness difference between two adjacent rings is too large to be properly manufactured.

In terms of producibility, the disks with a slot depth of 40 cm do not seem to be feasible. The reason for this is that a lot of material is needed around the axle and a sudden drop in thickness occurs. A way to

overcome this problem could be to design a larger disc so that there is more material around the axle. This might, on the other hand, reduce the ultimate speed due to the increase in dimensions.

The ultimate strength value might need an adjustment after the full-scale test is carried out for the verification of the ultimate load

The first eigenfrequencies of the disc are in all cases lower than the disk speed. This means that when reaching the operational speed and during slowing down the disc becomes unstable every time it passes through one of those frequencies. This problem can be overcome either by the addition of more material, which directly implies weight, to increase the bending stiffness of the disc, or by mechanical damping.

References

- [1] <http://europeanspallationsource.se>
- [2] <http://www.frm2.tum.de/en/science/spectrometry/toftof/index.html>
- [3] J.R.D.Copley and T.J. Udovic “Neutron Time-of-Flight Spectroscopy” *Journal of Research of the National Institute of Standards and Technologies*, Vol. 98, No1, pp 71-87, 1993
- [4] Antonelli V, Wedekind M, Kämer L, Baier H, “The Design of a CFRP Chopper Disk for a Time of Flight Spectrometer”, ICCM 18, 2011, Korea